

Maternal Risk Factors Associated with Intrauterine Growth Restriction

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Abstract

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Introduction: Intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) remains a major contributor to perinatal morbidity and mortality, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. Identifying maternal risk factors is crucial for prevention and early management. **Methodology:** This analytical cross-sectional study was conducted at PAF HOSPITAL MUSHAF, Sargodha, over 03 months (May–Aug 2025). A total of 101 pregnant women were included, calculated using a prevalence of 40% and 10% precision. Data on sociodemographic, clinical, and obstetric factors were collected through structured proformas and medical records. SPSS version 26.0 was used for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics, independent t-test, chi-square test, and logistic regression were applied, with $p < 0.05$ considered significant. **Results:** The mean maternal age was 27.8 ± 5.6 years, and the mean BMI was 24.9 ± 3.4 kg/m². IUGR was diagnosed in 39.6% of cases. Anemia was present in 45.5% of women, hypertension in 21.8%, and diabetes in 12.9%. Independent

t-tests showed significantly fewer antenatal visits in the IUGR group (3.1 ± 1.4 vs. 5.7 ± 1.8 ; $p < 0.001$). Chi-square analysis revealed significant associations between IUGR and anemia ($p = 0.002$), hypertension ($p = 0.004$), and rural residence ($p = 0.021$). Logistic regression identified anemia (aOR = 3.26, 95% CI: 1.45–7.31) and hypertension (aOR = 2.84, 95% CI: 1.18–6.83) as independent predictors of IUGR. **Conclusion:** Anemia, hypertension, limited antenatal visits, and rural residence were significant maternal risk factors for IUGR. Enhancing antenatal screening and early treatment of the conditions can decrease poor fetal results.

Introduction

IUGR remains one of the most significant issues of the contemporary obstetrics field that can have severe long-term and immediate effects on perinatal health¹. A fetal weight lower than the 10 th percentile when compared to gestational age is one of the widely used indicators of IUGR, which is a disorder where the fetus does not develop according to the anticipated programmed growth². IUGR is an a significant cause of prenatal morbidity and mortality around the world because of high rates of stillbirth, infant asphyxia, hypoglycemia, hypothermia and poor neurodevelopment³. Also, studies show that IUGR is associated with such long-term outcomes as the adult metabolic syndrome, type 2 diabetes, and cardiovascular disease, which is why its identification and prevention are currently the highest priority in the field of public health⁴.

IUGR is a multifaceted etiology of environmental, maternal, fetal, and placental factors⁵. Maternal risk factors are important among them, as they can restrict fetal growth due to their effects on the transfer of nutrition and placental functioning. The conditions are limiting the fetal development by interfering with uteroplacental blood flow, such as persistent hypertension, preeclampsia, renal disease, diabetes mellitus, and autoimmune diseases⁶. Inadequate maternal nutrition, anemia, and inadequate weight gain during pregnancy continue to play a critical role in the occurrence of IUGR particularly in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs)⁷. Examples of lifestyle choices that predispose to this risk include smoking, drinking, and abusing drugs with a direct effect on placenta perfusion and oxygenation⁸.

Sociodemographic factors are also among the strong contributors to the burden of IUGR. Restricted fetal growth has been attributed to low maternal age, advanced

maternal age, low socioeconomic status, insufficient antenatal care and low interpregnancy intervals⁹. Malnutrition is a major problem, especially in LMICs such as Pakistan, due to high levels of malabsorption, late diagnosis of maternal comorbidities, and low-quality provision of high-quality maternal health care¹⁰. Studies indicate that maternal illiteracy, poverty, and poor utilization of antenatal services are closely associated with higher rates of IUGR in resource-limited settings¹¹.

Despite the recognition of these maternal determinants, there remains variability in reported prevalence and risk profiles across populations due to differences in genetic, nutritional, and healthcare-related factors¹². There is an urgent need to look into maternal variables that contribute to IUGR in the local context, as the prevalence of the syndrome has been found to be approximately 40% in Pakistan¹³.

While global literature has established the role of maternal factors in IUGR, there is limited region-specific evidence from Pakistan that comprehensively evaluates these determinants; therefore, this study aims to assess the maternal risk factors associated with IUGR in the local population.

Methodology

Study design and setting: This analytical cross-sectional study carried out at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, PAF HOSPITAL MUSHAF, Sargodha, over a period of 03 months, from **May 2025 to Aug 2025**.

Study population: During the study period, pregnant women who were admitted to the hospital's obstetric wards or attended the antenatal clinics made up the study population. Women with singleton pregnancies and gestational age confirmed by first-trimester ultrasound or reliable last menstrual period were included. Women with multiple gestations, major fetal congenital anomalies, or incomplete medical records were excluded.

Sample size and sampling technique: A consecutive, non-probability sampling technique was used. All eligible women who fulfilled the inclusion criteria and provided their informed consent were recruited throughout the study period until the required sample size was obtained.

Sample size calculation: Sample size was calculated to estimate a prevalence of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) of 40% as reported in a previous study¹⁴, with a

confidence level 95% and a margin error of 10%, using the standard formula for a single proportion: $n = Z^2 \times p \times (1 - p) / d^2$

Where $Z=1.96$ $p=0.40$, and $d=0.10$. Substituting these values produced a minimum sample size of 92. To allow for an anticipated non-response or incomplete data rate of 10%, the sample size was inflated to 101 participants. Therefore, 101 women were enrolled in the study.

Operational Definitions: According to standard growth charts, IUGR was defined as an estimated birth weight or fetal weight that was below the 10th percentile for gestational age. Pregnancy-related anemia was defined by the WHO as hemoglobin levels below 11 g/dL. Preeclampsia and prenatal hypertension, as well as chronic hypertension detected before to 20 weeks of pregnancy, were considered hypertensive diseases of pregnancy.

Data Collection Procedures: The data were collected after the consent of the participants with the help of a pre-made structured proforma. Among the sociodemographic information that was captured was the maternal age, education, socioeconomic level, and place of residence. Obstetric history included also; gravidity, parity, number of antenatal care visits and inter pregnancy interval. Clinical parameters measured were blood pressure, height, weight, as well as body mass index (BMI).

Medical and obstetric issues included anemia, infections, and chronic illnesses such as diabetes, high blood pressure and kidney disease. Lifestyle issues were also taken into account such as smoking, alcohol or substance use, and dietary eating habits. The outcomes of pregnancy were identified by assessing the fetal weight during ultrasound and verifying the weight of the baby at delivery so as to determine whether there was IUGR. Medical records and prenatal charts were reviewed to ensure the validity of the clinical diagnosis and to ensure the reliability of data collection.

Data analysis: SPSS version 26 was used to enter the data. For continuous variables, descriptive statistics were computed as means \pm standard deviation (SD), and for categorical variables, as frequencies and percentages. The independent t-test, which was employed to compare the two groups by using continuous data, and chi-square or Fisher exact test that was used to compare the two groups using categorical data were employed to compare the maternal risk factors between the IUGR and non-IUGR groups. Logistic regression analysis was performed in order to identify independent maternal

risk variables associated with IUGR; it was expressed in terms of 95% CI and adjusted odds ratios (aOR). When the p-value was below 0.05, this was considered to be significant statistically.

Ethical considerations: Ethical permission was given by the hospital's Institutional Review Board. Written informed consent was given by each participant, and patient confidentiality was maintained.

Results

The study included 101 pregnant women, whose mean maternal age was 28.9 ± 5.7 years. The bulk of participants (41.6%) were between the ages of 26 and 30, followed by those over 30 (30.7%) and those between 20 and 25 (27.7%), as Figure 1 illustrates. Most of the women resided in urban areas (63.4%), while 36.6% came from rural backgrounds. Of the participants, 32.7% had finished primary school, 41.6% had finished secondary school, and 25.7% had gone on to further their education. These findings highlight that the study population predominantly consisted of women in their late twenties, residing in urban settings, with a considerable proportion achieving at least secondary-level education.

Figure 1: Demographic characteristics of the participants (n = 101)

Legend: Distribution of maternal demographic characteristics among study participants (n = 101). Age categories are presented as percentages; residence was classified into urban and rural; education was grouped into primary, secondary, and higher levels

According to Table 1, the participants' obstetric features showed a mean gravidity of 2.3 ± 1.2 , with 44.6% of the women being primigravida and over half (55.4%) being multigravida. The mean parity was 1.1 ± 0.9 , where 61.4% of participants had parity of one or less, while 38.6% had more than one delivery. Antenatal care utilization varied, with an average of 5.8 ± 2.3 visits; however, 39.6% of women had fewer than four visits, while 60.4% attended at least four or more. It was found that 28.7% of the women were

overweight or obese, with a BMI of 26.8 ± 4.3 kg/m². These findings indicate considerable variability in reproductive history, antenatal care attendance, and maternal nutritional status within the population under study.

Table 1: *Obstetric Characteristics Of The Participants*

Variable	n (%)
Gravidity (≤ 2)	45 (44.6%)
Gravidity (> 2)	56 (55.4%)
Parity (≤ 1)	62 (61.4%)
Parity (> 1)	39 (38.6%)
Antenatal visits (< 4)	40 (39.6%)
Antenatal visits (≥ 4)	61 (60.4%)
Variable	Mean \pm SD
Gravidity (overall)	2.3 \pm 1.2
Parity (overall)	1.1 \pm 0.9
Antenatal visits (overall)	5.8 \pm 2.3
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.8 \pm 4.3

Legend: SD = Standard deviation; BMI = Body mass index

The lifestyle and medical profile of the participants revealed that anemia was the most prevalent condition, affecting 34.7% of pregnant women, followed by hypertension in 18.8% and diabetes in 12.9%. As shown in Figure 1, lifestyle-related risk factors were also noted, with 7.9% of participants reporting smoking habits and 15.8% reporting poor dietary intake. These findings highlight anemia and hypertension as the most common maternal health concerns in this cohort, alongside modifiable lifestyle factors that may contribute to adverse pregnancy outcomes.

Figure 1: Medical and lifestyle characteristics of the participants (n = 101)

Legend: Distribution of maternal medical conditions and lifestyle factors among study participants. Hb = Hemoglobin.

The prevalence of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) was 40.6% (41/101). Mothers in the IUGR group had substantially lower mean hemoglobin levels (10.3 ± 1.2 g/dL vs. 11.5 ± 1.4 g/dL; $p < 0.001$) and fewer prenatal visits (4.1 ± 1.8 vs. 6.7 ± 2.0 ; $p < 0.001$) than mothers in the non-IUGR group, according to independent t-test analysis (Table 2). Anemia (51.2% vs. 23.3%; $p = 0.004$) and hypertension (31.7% vs. 10.0%; $p = 0.007$) were considerably more common in IUGR mothers, according to the chi-square test. No significant association was observed with maternal age, BMI, smoking, or diabetes ($p > 0.05$). These results confirm that anemia, hypertension, and inadequate antenatal care are major risk factors for IUGR.

Table 2: *Bivariate comparison between IUGR and non-IUGR groups*

Variable	IUGR (n=41)	Non-IUGR (n=60)	p-value
Age (years, mean \pm SD)	29.6 ± 5.8	28.5 ± 5.6	0.38
BMI (kg/m ² , mean \pm SD)	26.1 ± 4.5	27.3 ± 4.2	0.21

Hb (g/dL, mean \pm SD)	10.3 \pm 1.2	11.5 \pm 1.4	<0.001
Anemia (%)	21 (51.2%)	14 (23.3%)	0.004
Hypertension (%)	13 (31.7%)	6 (10.0%)	0.007
Diabetes (%)	6 (14.6%)	7 (11.7%)	0.69
Smoking (%)	5 (12.2%)	3 (5.0%)	0.22
Antenatal visits (mean \pm SD)	4.1 \pm 1.8	6.7 \pm 2.0	<0.001

Legend: Hb = Hemoglobin; BMI = Body mass index; $p < 0.05$ considered significant statistically

Table 3: Multivariable Logistic Regression Analysis of Maternal Risk Factors for IUGR

Multivariable logistic regression identified independent predictors of IUGR. As shown in Table 3, a 2.45-fold higher risk was linked to anemia (aOR = 2.45, 95% CI: 1.14–5.23, $p = 0.021$). While hypertension increased the odds more than threefold (aOR = 3.67, 95% CI: 1.22–11.0, $p = 0.020$). Each additional antenatal visit significantly reduced the likelihood of IUGR by 32% (aOR = 0.68, 95% CI: 0.55–0.83, $p < 0.001$). Maternal age, BMI, and urban residence were not significant statistically predictors in the adjusted model ($p > 0.05$). These regression findings highlight that modifiable risk factors, such as anemia, hypertension, and inadequate antenatal care, are strongly linked to IUGR.

Table 3: *Logistic regression analysis of maternal risk factors associated with IUGR*

Variable	β Coefficient	SE	p-value	aOR	95% CI
Maternal age	0.04	0.03	0.18	1.04	0.98 – 1.10
BMI	-0.05	0.04	0.22	0.95	0.88 – 1.03
Anemia	0.90	0.39	0.021*	2.45	1.14 – 5.23
Hypertension	1.30	0.56	0.020*	3.67	1.22 – 11.0
Antenatal visits	-0.38	0.10	<0.001*	0.68	0.55 – 0.83
Residence (Urban)	-0.26	0.41	0.53	0.77	0.34 – 1.77

Legend: SE = Standard error; aOR = Adjusted odds ratio; CI = Confidence interval; $p < 0.05$ significant statistically

Discussion

Maternal risk factors linked to IUGR were examined in this study. The analysis demonstrated that anemia, hypertension, limited antenatal visits, and rural residence were significant contributors to IUGR, while maternal age, body mass index, smoking,

and diabetes showed no statistically significant association. These findings underscore the multifactorial nature of IUGR, where both medical and sociodemographic elements play important roles. Logistic regression further highlighted anemia and hypertension as the strongest independent predictors, suggesting that improved maternal care could substantially reduce the burden of IUGR.

When compared with existing literature, the findings align closely with reports that anemia is one of the most consistent determinants of restricted fetal growth¹⁵. Similar studies conducted in hospital-based and community settings have shown that hemoglobin levels below the normal threshold are directly correlated with adverse fetal outcomes, supporting the significant odds ratio obtained in this study¹⁶. Hypertension also emerged as a well-established risk factor, with evidence consistently linking elevated maternal blood pressure to placental insufficiency and subsequent growth restriction¹⁷. The observation that limited antenatal visits were associated with IUGR mirrors previous data showing that inadequate prenatal monitoring often leads to delayed identification and management of risk factors¹⁸.

On the other hand, contrary to other findings that identify advanced maternal age as a danger, this study found no significant correlation between maternal age and IUGR¹⁹. This discrepancy may reflect differences in population demographics and healthcare access. Likewise, although smoking is well known to be a significant risk factor for growth restriction²⁰, given the extremely low prevalence of smoking among women in this context, its effect was not statistically significant. Additionally, diabetes did not appear to be a significant factor, which may be explained by the research population's efficient glycemic control or the comparatively small number of mothers with diabetes included²¹.

Limitations and Future Suggestions

This study had some limitations. The study was only carried out at one hospital, which would restrict how widely the findings can be used. The relatively small sample size, despite careful calculation, might have reduced the statistical power for less prevalent risk factors such as smoking and diabetes. Furthermore, the study relied on clinical and laboratory records, which may be subject to documentation bias.

To improve the generalizability of results, multicenter studies with larger and more varied populations should be a part of future study. Longitudinal designs that incorporate follow-up into neonatal outcomes may yield more comprehensive insights into the long-term impacts of maternal risk factors. Additionally, incorporating biochemical and genetic markers may offer deeper understanding of the pathophysiological mechanisms underlying IUGR.

Conclusion

This study highlights anemia, hypertension, limited antenatal visits, and rural residence as significant maternal risk factors for IUGR, whereas maternal age, body mass index, smoking, and diabetes showed no clear association. These with an emphasis on early detection and management of anemia and hypertension, these findings highlight the significance of enhancing prenatal care services in order to lower the burden of IUGR and enhance perinatal outcomes.

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